

Search for Fluorescent Brighteners-I*. Synthesis of 2-(3'-Coumarinyl)Benzoxazoles and Their Fluorescence

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2-(3'-Coumarinyl)benzoxazoles have been synthesised by the condensation of various *o*-aminophenols with simple and substituted coumarin-3-carboxylic acids using polyphosphoric acid as the cyclodehydrating agent. These compounds have been characterised by U. V., I. R. and N. M. R. spectra. Fluorescence emission spectra of the compounds have also been recorded.

HETEROCYCLIC compounds consisting of benzoxazole and coumarin moieties have gained considerable commercial importance in recent years as fluorescent brighteners especially for synthetic fibres. 2-(3'-phenylcoumarin-7'-yl) and 2-(3'-coumarinyl)benzoxazoles^{1,2} have been patented as optical brighteners for polyesters, polyamides and polyvinyl chloride. Compounds in which the 3-position of coumarin is linked, through a *p*-phenylene bridge, to the 2-position of benzoxazole have been shown to be brilliant fluorescent brighteners³. In our present investigation, synthesis of 2-(3'-coumarinyl)benzoxazoles carrying various substituents has been carried out to study their fluorescence characteristics and to evaluate their possible use as fluorescent brighteners.

Polyphosphoric acid (PPA) has been found to be an excellent cyclodehydrating agent for the synthesis of 2-arylbenzoxazoles⁴ from *o*-aminophenol and aromatic carboxylic acids. The synthesis was achieved by heating a mixture of appropriate *o*-aminophenols (I) and simple and substituted coumarin-3-carboxylic acids (II) and 5,6-benzocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid using PPA as the cyclodehydrating agent⁵.

A few lines about the preparation of the requisite aminophenols are mentioned here. 2-Amino-6-methylphenol⁶ and 2-amino-4-methylphenol⁷ have been prepared by reduction of the corresponding nitro compounds using sodium dithionite.

Halogen substituted 2-aminophenols as 2-amino-6-chlorophenol, 2-amino-4-chlorophenol, 2-amino-4,6-di-chlorophenol, 2-amino-4-bromophenol, 2-amino-4,6-dibromophenol, 2-amino-4-methyl-6-bromophenol have been prepared by reducing the corresponding nitrophenols with hydrazine in presence of Raney nickel catalyst.⁸

Coumarin-3-carboxylic acids (II) have been prepared by condensing the appropriate salicylaldehyde with either malonic acid⁹ or malonic ester¹⁰ in presence of a base.

Experimental

General Method for the Reduction of the Halogen or Phenyl Substituted o-nitrophenols :

The *o*-nitrophenol was dissolved in about 10 times the amount of methanol containing a small amount of Raney nickel, and 100% hydrazine hydrate (3 equivalents) was added drop by drop with shaking. After the addition was over, the mixture was refluxed gently till the colour of the solution was discharged (30-60 min.). The solution

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was filtered while hot to remove the catalyst, concentrated and cooled to yield the crystals of the amino compound.

General Method of Preparation of Coumarin-3-Carboxylic Acid :

The salicylaldehyde was mixed with malonic acid (2 equivalents) in absolute ethanol and freshly distilled aniline (1 equivalent) was added, the reaction mixture was shaken well for 5 minutes and kept aside for 24 hr. Then it was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered. The product obtained was recrystallised from water or aqueous alcohol.

Method for the Preparation of 2-(3'-coumarinyl)-benzoxazoles :

An equimolecular mixture of coumarin-3-carboxylic acid and *o*-aminophenol was heated with 10 times the weight of polyphosphoric acid⁶ at 150° for 2 hr and then at 200° for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into water. The separated product was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and recrystallised (see Table 1).

I. R. Spectra :

The I. R. spectra of the compounds were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model 137 spectrophotometer in KBr. All the compounds show characteristic absorptions in the region 1760-1725, 1623-1580 and 1130-1020 cm^{-1} . The absorption at 1760-1725 cm^{-1} is due to the lactone carbonyl of the coumarin ring. In most of the cases the absorption occurs at 1740 cm^{-1} . The absorption at 1620-1580 cm^{-1} is assigned to the $-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ stretching. Most of the compounds have this band at 1600 cm^{-1} . The

absorption at 1130-1020 cm^{-1} is assigned to the stretching of $-\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}-$ group which is present in the oxazole as well as in the coumarin ring.

N. M. R. Spectra :

The N.M.R. spectrum of a representative sample of 2-(3'-coumarinyl)-7-methylbenzoxazole has been recorded on Varian A-60 N.M.R. spectrophotometer in CDCl_3 solution using TMS as internal standard. It gives a singlet at δ 2.8 for 3 protons assigned to the 7-methyl; a multiplet at δ 7.23-7.83 for 7 protons assigned to the aromatic protons and a singlet at δ 8.73 for one proton assigned to the vinyl proton at the 4 position of the coumarin ring.

U. V. Spectra :

U. V. spectra of all the compounds listed in Table 1 were recorded on Beckmann DK 2A spectrophotometer using methanol as the solvent and the values are recorded.

All the compounds studied herein exhibit characteristic absorption at around 355 nm, 261 nm and 211 nm. In most cases there appears an inflexion around 324 nm.

The absorption maximum of simple benzoxazole is at 276 nm; unsubstituted coumarin has its absorption maximum at 310 nm and the absorption maximum of the compound obtained by the combination of these two moieties, 2-(3'-coumarinyl)-benzoxazole, is at 350 nm. 2-Styryl-benzoxazole has absorption max. at 345 nm. 2-(3'-coumarinyl)-benzoxazole may be visualised as a derivative of 2-styryl-benzoxazole, bridged by a $-\text{CO}-\text{O}-$ group. The bathochromic shift caused in the former by 5 nm may be attributed to the increased planarity

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	2-(3'-coumarinyl)-benzoxazole	% Yield	*m.p. °C	Solvent of Crystallisation	U.V. max nm	log _e max	Fluorescence emission max nm	Colour of Fluorescence
1.	(Unsubstituted).	80	186	Aqueous ethanol	349	4.25	445	Greenish Blue
2.	7-Methyl-	83	195	Ethanol	350	4.31	452	Greenish Blue
3.	4-Methyl-	85	185	Aqueous dioxan	350	4.13	461	Greenish Blue
4.	7-Chloro-	75	185	Ethanol	340	4.20	437	Blue
5.	5,7-Dichloro-	73	210	Aqueous ethanol	349	4.28	434	Blue
6.	5-Bromo-	78	218	Dioxan	350	4.56	439	Blue
7.	5,7-Dibromo-	70	243	Dioxan	350	4.26	442	Greenish Blue
8.	5-Methyl-7-bromo-	82	206	Aqueous dioxan	348	4.25	451	Greenish Blue
9.	5-Bromo-7-methyl-	80	214	Dioxan	353	4.11	450	Greenish Blue
10.	5-Phenyl-	74	186	Aqueous dioxan	355	4.28	459	Greenish Blue
11.	6'-Bromo-	84	234	Aqueous dioxan	360	4.24	449	Greenish Blue
12.	6'-Bromo-5-methyl-	81	240	Dioxan	362	4.41	454	Greenish Blue
13.	6'-Bromo-5-chloro-	69	265	Aqueous dioxan	358	4.53	457	Greenish Blue
14.	6',8'-Dibromo-	72	260	Dioxan	345	4.20	459	Greenish Blue
15.	5',6'-Benzo-	78	250	Benzene	391	4.40	474	Green

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

of the molecule caused by the bridging and consequent more effective delocalisation of π -electrons.

Substituents on the coumarin are more effective than on the benzoxazole ring, in causing bathochromic shift in the absorption maxima.

2-(5', 6'-Benzo-3'-coumarinyl)benzoxazole has absorption max. at 391 nm and thus the red shift caused by the presence of the additional fused benzene ring on the coumarin part is 42 nm.

Fluorescence Emission spectra :

As a method of primary evaluation of the possible use of the compounds synthesised as optical brighteners, their fluorescence emission spectra were recorded. An ideal fluorescent brightener should have a strong absorption in the near U.V. region (340-400 nm) and emission in the blue region (415-465 nm)¹¹. The spectra were recorded on a Beckmann DK 2A spectrophotometer using mercury lamp as the exciting radiation source and dioxane as the solvent.

Attempts have been made to study the effect of structure on fluorescence emission maxima. All the compounds exhibit brilliant fluorescence in the blue region. The values are recorded in Table 1.

2-(3'-coumarinyl)benzoxazole has its emission max. at 445 nm. Alkyl substituents on the benzoxazole ring cause a red shift in the emission max., while chloro or bromo substitutions have the opposite effect. The introduction of a fused benzene ring on the coumarin part causes a bathochromic shift by about 30 nm, and the color of the fluorescence is shifted from blue to the green

range. As all the 2-(3'-coumarinyl)benzoxazoles have absorption and emission in the required range, they may be used as fluorescent brighteners.

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